

Evaluation of Low-Cost Custom Made VAC Therapy Compared with Conventional Wound Dressings in the Treatment of Non-Healing Lower Limb Ulcers in lower Socio-Economic Group Patients

Devanshu Sojitra¹, Deepak J. Vora², Shashikant V. Umraniya³, Deep V. Patel⁴

¹3rd Year surgical Resident, SCL Hospital, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

²Associate Professor, SCL Hospital, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

³Assistant Professor, SCL Hospital, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

⁴1st Year Surgical Resident, SCL Hospital, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 25-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Deepak J. Vora,

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The purpose of this study is to shown efficacy of vacuum- assisted closure (VAC) therapy compared with conventional wound dressings for fast healing of non-healing lower limb ulcers in lower socio-economic group patients.

Methods: Our study was conducted on 40 patients divided in 2 groups of 20 each to compare VAC dressing with conventional dressings.

Results: Majority of wounds in VAC group got closed in average 6 weeks. Patient satisfaction was excellent in the majority of patients in VAC group compared to those in conventional dressing group.

Conclusions: So, VAC dressing was found to be more beneficial to patient than conventional dressings. Patient satisfaction was excellent in the majority of patients in VAC group compared to those in conventional dressing group.

Keywords: Vacuum Assisted Closure Dressing, Conventional Dressings, Wounds.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Background

Negative-pressure wound therapy is a technique to achieve wound healing in patients with non-healing wounds which defined as “a wound that does not heal within the expected time frame, typically within four to six weeks” of the lower limb; VAC therapy is a technique to accelerate the healing of non-healing ulcers that fail to heal on their own (primary healing), Applying intermittent negative pressure of approximately (-125) mmHg appears to hasten healing and the formation of granulation tissue in chronic wounds, ulcers and debrided wound. [1]

A mainstay of treatment of non-healing ulcers is treatment of underlying cause (diabetic control , avoid trauma and injury ,treatment of chronic infections) and meticulous debridement of all necrotic, devitalized and fibrous tissue, with a primary goal to obtain healing of ulcer and ultimately closure of wound. [2]

Management of non-healing ulcers differs in different institutions; hence, optimal treatment is ill-defined. [3,4]

In VAC therapy, the application of topical negative pressure (vacuum) removes blood and serous fluid, reduces infection rates (closed/sealed system creates a hypoxic environment), further increasing localized

blood flow, thereby supplying the wound with oxygen and nutrition to promote accelerated healing. [5,-8]

The optimal topical therapy for non-healing lower limb ulcers remains poorly defined. Saline-moistened gauze has been the standard method; however, it has been difficult to continuously maintain a moist wound environment with these dressings. [9]

Subsequently, various dressing techniques like growth factors, hydrocolloid wound gels, enzymatic debridement compounds, hyperbaric oxygen therapy, cultured skin substitutes, and other wound therapies have been advocated. All of these therapies are expensive and time consuming also, there is little scientific evidence to support their efficacy. [10]

Negative pressure wound therapy (NPWT): Using the vacuum-assisted closure (VAC) has shown good results in the management of non-healing ulcers. [11]

We conducted comparative study to evaluate the role of VAC in comparison to conventional dressings in the healing of non-healing ulcers of

lower limb in lower socio- economic group patients. [12,13]

Material and Methods

This study was comparative study which was conducted by General surgery Department of our institute (SCL HOSPITAL), Saraspur, Ahmedabad, which is a tertiary care hospital. Our study was conducted between MAY 2022 and JUNE 2023, 40 patients were treated for non-healing lower limb ulcers Wagner grade 1 (Superficial Diabetic Ulcer) and 2 (Ulcer extension Involves ligament, tendon, joint capsule or fascia No abscess or Osteomyelitis).

The total number of patients admitted were 40. 20 cases got VAC dressing application and remaining 20 were managed with conventional dressings. These 40 patients were divided in 2 groups, group A and group B by randomization alternatively as per their presentation to the hospital in VAC dressings and conventional dressings respectively.

Inclusion Criteria

- Wounds treated with VAC in our study included:
- Diabetic foot ulcers.
- Pressure sores.
- Traumatic ulcers.
- Fasciotomy wounds. Wounds post-drainage for abscess with exposure of deep structures such as tendon and fascia.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with previous VAC therapy and those on other forms of advanced wound therapy like hyperbaric oxygen therapy, normothermic wound therapy, or growth factor therapy within 30 days of the study, start date were excluded.
- Patients on corticosteroids, immunosuppressive agents, or chemotherapeutic agents and patients with poorly controlled medical problems were also excluded from the study.
- Patients with malignancy in the wound, untreated osteomyelitis. Wounds with exposed arteries or veins.
- Patients on anticoagulants or with actively bleeding wounds.

Step 1: Preparation of Wound Bed: Old dressing from the wound was removed and discarded. A culture swab for microbiology was taken before wound irrigation with normal saline. Proper antibiotics given according to sensitivity.

Surface slough or necrotic tissue was surgically removed (minor surgical debridement) and adequate haemostasis achieved. Skin around ulcer was cleaned with spirit. Betadine, H₂O₂ and Eusol dressing was placed to remove slough and devitalised tissue.

Step 2: Foam Placement: Sterile, foam dressing was gently placed into the wound cavity to provide an even distribution of negative pressure over the entire wound bed to aid in wound healing. Polyurethane ether (PU), was used in our study. Suction tube was embedded in the foam which was then connected to a controlled vacuum pump with a gauge meter for pressure control. The amount of pressure applied ranged from 120 to 130 mmHg.

Step 3: Placement of Adhesive Dressing for Wound Sealing: The site is then sealed with an adhesive drape. In our study, we used iodine-impregnated adhesive dressing (Ioban, 3M) which covered at least 5 to 7 cm of surrounding healthy skin to ensure effective seal. Separate drapes were used for suction tube and covered. (fig.3)

Dressing was changed every 48 to 72 h or sooner if the dressing got soaked. Care was taken when removing the adhesive drape to avoid irritating the peri-wound skin.

VAC dressing was kept for over a period of 2–7 weeks intermittently. Ulcers were treated until the wound closed spontaneously, surgically or until completion of the 30 day period, whichever was earlier. After wound closure, patients were followed on a regular basis.

Patients who were discharged from the hospital after wound closure were followed twice weekly, then weekly, followed by every 2 weeks, and then monthly.

Follow-up was done for up to 6 months. Treatment success was defined as wound closure within a period of 7 weeks.

Figure 1: Instruments required for VAC. Dressing set, suction tube with side pores (ryle's tube / suction catheter), loban and sterile foam

Figure 2: In-hospital suctioning unit for VAC. Pressure gauge for monitoring VAC pressure

Figure 3: Placement of adhesive dressing for wound sealing over lower limb

Results

• **Age distribution:** In our study, out of 40 patients, in VAC group was between 45 and 70 years with mean age of 56.4 While in conventional dressing

group age, range was between 40 and 64 years with average of 52.2 years. Mean age of patients was slightly more in VAC group as compared to conventional dressing group.(table no.1)

Table 1: Age distribution of patients

	Age group in year	Median age group in year
VAC	45-70	56.4
Conventional	40-64	52.2

• **Causes of ulcers:** In our study, diabetic ulcer is most common cause of non-healing ulcer of lower limb with 30 patients (75%); rest are traumatic and pressure ulcer and fasciotomy wounds as mentioned below (table no.2)

Table 2: Showing causes of ulcer

Causes of ulcer	VAC therapy	Conventional wound dressing
Diabetic foot Ulcer	16(40%)	14(35%)
Pressure sores	2(5%)	3(7.5%)
Traumatic ulcers	1(2.5%)	2(5%)
Fasciotomy wounds	1(2.5%)	1%(2.5%)

• Comparison of average duration of hospital stay in VAC group is 40 days while in conventional group is 60 days.(table no.3)

reached to 100 % by the end of week 7. While in conventional dressing group, only 35 % of patients showed granulation tissue by the end of week 2 which further reached to 60 % by the end of week 7

• Granulation tissue appeared in 60 % of patients in VAC group by the end of week 2 which further

Table 3: Frequency distribution of appearance of granulation tissue in different groups

	Week 2 (%)	Week 7 (%)
VAC	12(60) %	20(100)%
Conventional	07(35)%	12(60)%

• The patients treated with VAC dressing in study showed comparable wound reduction capabilities with an average wound size reduction of 56 % in comparison to conventional dressing group which had average wound size reduction of 29%.

Before

After

Figure 1: Showing faster granulation tissue and healing in VAC dressing patients

Discussion

The ability of regular VAC dressings in promoting wound bed granulation and healing has been demonstrated in several studies. Application of VAC over the ulcer allows the arterioles to dilate, increasing local circulation, promoting angiogenesis, reduces bacterial burden and chronic interstitial wound fluid which finally leads to increased granulation tissue over the wound. Wound bed optimization is crucial in preventing ulcer complications and favors eventual wound closure either by split-tissue skin grafting or by secondary intention. [14]

In our study, we observed that the patients on VAC therapy had the early appearance of granulation tissue as compared to the patients treated by moist saline gauze dressings. Complete (100 %) granulation was achieved earlier and in a higher proportion of patients in VAC group as compared to conventional dressing group. [15]

Thus, rate of disappearance of wound discharge was faster in VAC group compared to conventional dressing group. VAC is generally well tolerated and, with few complications. [16]

Conclusion

The application of VAC had shown good results in our study and patient had good compliance compared to conventional dressing.

Patient satisfaction was excellent in the majority of patients in VAC group as it is low-cost, low-frequent dressing changes, faster healing and lower hospital stay compared to those in conventional dressing group.

References

1. Brem H, Sheehan P, Rosenberg HJ, Schneider JS, Boulton AJ. Evidence-based protocol for

diabetic foot ulcers. *Plast Reconstr Surg.* 2006; 117:193–209S.

2. Argenta LC, Morykwas MJ. V.A.C.uum-assisted closure: a new method for wound control and treatment: clinical experience. *Ann Plast Surg.* 1997;38:563–76.
3. Armstrong DG, Lavery LA. Diabetic Foot Study Consortium. Negative pressure wound therapy after partial diabetic foot amputation: a multicentre, randomised controlled trial. *Lancet.* 2005;366:1704–10.
4. Eginton MT, Brown KR, Seabrook GR, Towne JB, Cambria RA. A prospective randomized evaluation of negative-pressure wound dressings for diabetic foot wounds. *Ann Vasc Surg.* 2003;17:645–9.
5. Morykwas MJ, Argenta LC, Shelton-Brown EI, McGuirt W. V.A.C.uum-assisted closure: a new method for wound control and treatment: animal studies and basic foundation. *Ann Plast Surg.* 1997;38:553–62.
6. American Diabetes Association. Consensus development conference on diabetic foot wound care. *Diabetes Care.* 1999;22:1354–60.
7. Ramanujam CL, Stapleton JJ, Zgonis T. Negative-pressure wound therapy in the management of diabetic Charcot foot and ankle wounds. *Diabet Foot Ankle.* 2013;4:20878.
8. Fabian TS, Kaufman HJ, Lett ED, Thomas JB, Rawl DK, Lewis PL, et al. The evaluation of subatmospheric pressure and hyperbaric oxygen in ischemic full-thickness wound healing. *AmSurg.* 2000;66(12):1136–43.
9. White R, McIntosh C. Topical therapies for diabetic foot ulcers: standard treatments. *J Wound Care.* 2008;17:426–32.
10. Mullner T, Mrkonjic L, Kwasny O, Vecsei V. The use of negative pressure to promote the healing of tissue defects: a clinical trial using the vacuum sealing technique. *Br J Plast Surg.* 1997;50(3):194–9.

11. Singh M, Singh R, Singh S, Pandey V, Singh D. Vacuum assisted closure in wound management-Poor man's VAC©. *Internet J Plast Surg.* 2009;6:1.
12. Mark TE, Kellie RB, Gary RS, Jonathan BT, Robert AC. Prospective randomized evaluation of negative-pressure wound dressing for diabetic foot wounds. *Ann Vasc Surg.* 2003;17:645–9.
13. Blume PA, Walters J, Payne W, Ayala J, Lantis J. Comparison of negative pressure wound therapy using V.A.C.uum-assisted closure with advanced moist wound therapy in the treatment of diabetic foot ulcers: a multicenter randomized controlled trial. *Diabetes Care.* 2008;31:631–6.
14. Wagner FW. The dysvascular foot: a system for diagnosis and treatment. *Foot Ankle.* 1981;2:64–122.
15. Peyceru T, Tardat E, Lepront D, Schwartz A, Jarry J, Durand-Dastes F. Vacuum-assisted abdominal closure in the critically ill patient. The poor man's VAC]. [Article in French] (Paris). *J Chir.* 2008;145(2):188–9.
16. Prabhdeep SN, Sanjeev KU, Ramneesh G, Kuljyot B, Shirin G. Role of negative pressure wound therapy in healing of diabetic foot ulcers. *J Surg Tech Case Rep.* 2011;3:17–22